

A NEW FORMULA FOR THE SUM OF INTEGER POWERS BASED ON ELEMENTARY MATRIX THEORY

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Abstract

In this study, we present a novel formula for the sum of the k -th powers of the first n positive integers, denoted as $S(n, k)$. Unlike existing formulations that employ binomial expansions, generating functions, or make use of special numbers such as Bernoulli or Stirling numbers, our approach leverages fundamental principles from elementary matrix theory. Additionally, we demonstrate that for very large values of n , the derived formula can be partially simplified. By contrasting our findings with a previously established Bernoulli-type formula, we ultimately derive a new combinatorial identity.

1. Introduction

Our investigation begins with the well-established expression for $S(n, k)$, defined as the sum of the k -th powers of the first n positive integers:

$$S(n, k) = 1^k + 2^k + \cdots + n^k.$$

The formulas for $S(n, k)$ have been the subject of extensive study over several centuries [3, 6, 9, 11]. In the past decade, numerous researchers have continued to

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explore the derivation of new formulas as well as the proof of existing ones from various methodologies [2, 4, 5, 7, 8, 10]. A prominent formula in this domain is derived from Pascal's identity in conjunction with the binomial theorem, given by

$$S(n, k) = \frac{n^{k+1}}{k+1} + \sum_{r=0}^{k-1} \binom{k}{r} \frac{(-1)^{k-r+1}}{k-r+1} S(n, r). \tag{1}$$

This expression reveals a clear recurrence relation between $S(n, k)$ and $S(n, r)$ (see Equation (1)), thus, the computation of $S(n, k)$ necessitates the prior determination of $S(n, r)$. Comprehensive analyses and proofs concerning this formula can be found in references [7, 8].

Subsequently, several researchers have sought to develop new formulas that eliminate these recurrence relations, introducing novel elements such as Bernoulli numbers [3, 9], Stirling numbers [5, 10], and hyperharmonic numbers [4]. Some of these formulations are expressed in the following equations:

$$S(n, k) = \frac{n^{k+1}}{k+1} + \frac{n^k}{2} + \sum_{i=2}^k \frac{B_i}{i} \binom{k}{i-1} n^{k-i+1}, \tag{2}$$

$$S(n, k) = \sum_{r=0}^k r! \left\{ \begin{matrix} k \\ r \end{matrix} \right\} \binom{n+1}{r+1}, \tag{3}$$

$$S(n, k) = \frac{(-1)^{k+1}}{k+1} \sum_{j=1}^{k+1} (-1)^j j! \left\{ \begin{matrix} k+1 \\ j \end{matrix} \right\} \left(H_{j+1}^{(n)} - \frac{1}{j+1} \right). \tag{4}$$

In these equations, B_i represents the Bernoulli numbers, $\left\{ \begin{matrix} k \\ r \end{matrix} \right\}$ denotes the Stirling numbers of the second kind, and $H_{j+1}^{(n)}$ signifies the $(j+1)$ -th hyperharmonic number. Detailed discussions and proofs of these formulas are available in the cited references.

A close examination of the derivation processes for formulas (1)-(4) reveals that they predominantly rely on binomial expansions, generating functions, or the utilization of special numbers. In contrast, our study derives a new formula for $S(n, k)$ through the lens of matrix theory, employing several key results related to matrix traces. Furthermore, we establish a new combinatorial identity by juxtaposing our simplified formula with a previously established Bernoulli-type expression.

2. Preliminaries

2.1. Relationship Between $S(n, k)$ and the Trace of Matrices

It is well-established that real-valued $n \times n$ diagonal matrices contain nonzero entries exclusively on their main diagonal, with all off-diagonal elements equal to

zero. Consider a diagonal matrix A whose main diagonal consists of the elements $1, 2, \dots, n$:

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 0 & 2 & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \cdots & n \end{bmatrix}.$$

Utilizing the fundamental rules of matrix multiplication, we find that the k -th power of matrix A is given by

$$A^k = \begin{bmatrix} 1^k & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 0 & 2^k & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \cdots & n^k \end{bmatrix}.$$

From the definition of the trace of a matrix, we can derive the following relationship:

$$\text{Tr}(A^k) = 1^k + 2^k + \cdots + n^k = S(n, k).$$

This relation indicates that the analysis of the formula for $S(n, k)$ can be transformed into an investigation of the trace $\text{Tr}(A^k)$. For small values of k , such as $k = 1, 2, 3$, the traces are well-known:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Tr}(A^1) &= 1^1 + 2^1 + \cdots + n^1 = \frac{n(n+1)}{2}, \\ \text{Tr}(A^2) &= 1^2 + 2^2 + \cdots + n^2 = \frac{n(n+1)(2n+1)}{6}, \\ \text{Tr}(A^3) &= 1^3 + 2^3 + \cdots + n^3 = \frac{n^2(n+1)^2}{4}. \end{aligned}$$

However, for larger values of k ($k > 3$), obtaining a general formula becomes increasingly complex. Insights from a previously established theorem discussed in Section 2.2, which presents two formulas characterizing the traces of 2×2 real-valued matrices raised to the k -th power, will be instrumental in advancing our study.

2.2. A Previously Established Theorem

Theorem 1. For any positive integer m and for 2×2 real-valued matrices M , the following relations hold:

$$\text{Tr}(M^{2m}) = (2m) \sum_{r=0}^m \frac{(-1)^r (2m-r-1)!}{r! (2m-2r)!} [\text{Det}(M)]^r [\text{Tr}(M)]^{2m-2r}, \quad (5)$$

and

$$\text{Tr}(M^{2m+1}) = (2m+1) \sum_{r=0}^m \frac{(-1)^r (2m-r)!}{r! (2m+1-2r)!} [\text{Det}(M)]^r [\text{Tr}(M)]^{2m+1-2r}, \quad (6)$$

where $\text{Tr}(\cdot)$ and $\text{Det}(\cdot)$ denote the trace and determinant of the corresponding matrices, respectively.

Proof. The proof of the formulas presented in Theorem 1 can be established using the method of mathematical induction. A comprehensive explanation of the proof can be found in reference [1]. \square

2.3. Decomposition of $S(n, k)$

To utilize the conclusions derived from Theorem 1 in formulating a new expression for $\text{Tr}(A^k)$, it is necessary to restrict the dimension of matrix A to 2×2 or to decompose the $n \times n$ matrix A into smaller 2×2 matrices. Consequently, since $\text{Tr}(A^k) = S(n, k)$, we can express $S(n, k)$ as the sum of the traces of these decomposed 2×2 matrices.

Lemma 1. *For any positive integer k and even positive integer n , $S(n, k)$ can be expressed as the sum of $\lfloor n/2 \rfloor$ traces of 2×2 real-valued matrices,*

$$S(n, k) = \text{Tr}(M_1^k) + \text{Tr}(M_2^k) + \cdots + \text{Tr}(M_s^k),$$

where $s = \lfloor n/2 \rfloor$, and $M_i = \begin{bmatrix} i & 0 \\ 0 & 2s + 1 - i \end{bmatrix}$ are 2×2 real-valued matrices for $1 \leq i \leq s$.

Proof. Let $n = 2s$. Thus, we can rewrite $S(n, k)$ as

$$S(n, k) = 1^k + 2^k + \cdots + (2s)^k.$$

The $2s$ terms in $S(n, k)$ can be grouped into $s = \lfloor n/2 \rfloor$ pairs. For each pair, such as $i^k + (2s + 1 - i)^k$, we have $M_i = \begin{bmatrix} i & 0 \\ 0 & 2s + 1 - i \end{bmatrix}$, leading to the relation

$$i^k + (2s + 1 - i)^k = \text{Tr}(M_i^k).$$

Since there are different M_i s, we conclude that

$$S(n, k) = \text{Tr}(M_1^k) + \text{Tr}(M_2^k) + \cdots + \text{Tr}(M_s^k),$$

where M_1, M_2, \dots, M_s are 2×2 real-valued matrices for all $1 \leq i \leq s$. So, Lemma 1 holds. \square

Lemma 2. *For any positive integer k and odd positive integer n , $S(n, k)$ can be expressed as the sum of $\lfloor n/2 \rfloor$ traces of 2×2 real-valued matrices, plus n^k ,*

$$S(n, k) = \text{Tr}(M_1^k) + \text{Tr}(M_2^k) + \cdots + \text{Tr}(M_s^k) + n^k,$$

where $s = \lfloor n/2 \rfloor$, and M_i are 2×2 real-valued matrices for $1 \leq i \leq s$.

Proof. Since n is odd, we can set $n = 2s + 1$, where s is a positive integer. Thus, we can rewrite $S(n, k)$ as

$$S(n, k) = 1^k + 2^k + \dots + (2s)^k + (2s + 1)^k.$$

By focusing on the first $2s$ terms, we can apply a procedure analogous to that used in the proof of Lemma 1. Therefore, we establish that

$$S(n, k) = \text{Tr}(M_1^k) + \text{Tr}(M_2^k) + \dots + \text{Tr}(M_s^k) + n^k,$$

where M_1, M_2, \dots, M_s are 2×2 real-valued matrices for all $1 \leq i \leq s$. Thus, Lemma 2 holds. \square

2.4. Definition of the Function $W(n, r)$

In this section, we introduce the function $W(n, r)$, which is a crucial component in our derived formula. The function is defined as

$$W(n, r) = \sum_{i=1}^n \left[\left(\frac{i}{n+1} \right)^r \left(1 - \frac{i}{n+1} \right)^r \right].$$

Letting $x_i = \frac{i}{n+1}$ and $f(x_i) = x_i^r(1 - x_i)^r$, we note that since $1 \leq i \leq n$, it follows that $0 < x_i < 1$. The function $f(x) = x^r(1 - x)^r$ is characterized by a symmetrical shape around $x = 0.5$. Consequently, when n is even, $W(n, r)$ can be rewritten as

$$W(n, r) = f(x_1) + f(x_2) + \dots + f(x_{n/2}) + f(x_{n/2+1}) + \dots + f(x_{n-1}) + f(x_n).$$

From the definition of x_i , we can deduce the following relationships:

$$\begin{aligned} x_1 + x_n &= \frac{1}{n+1} + \frac{n}{n+1} = \frac{1+n}{n+1} = 1 = 2 \times 0.5 \\ \text{implies } f(x_1) &= f(x_n), \\ x_2 + x_{n-1} &= \frac{2}{n+1} + \frac{n-1}{n+1} = \frac{1+n}{n+1} = 1 = 2 \times 0.5 \\ \text{implies } f(x_2) &= f(x_{n-1}), \\ &\vdots \\ x_{n/2} + x_{n/2+1} &= \frac{n/2}{n+1} + \frac{n/2+1}{n+1} = \frac{n+1}{n+1} = 1 = 2 \times 0.5 \\ \text{implies } f(x_{n/2}) &= f(x_{n/2+1}). \end{aligned}$$

Thus, we conclude that

$$\sum_{i=1}^{n/2} \left[\left(\frac{i}{n+1} \right)^r \left(1 - \frac{i}{n+1} \right)^r \right] = \frac{W(n, r)}{2}.$$

3. Main results

3.1. A New Formula for $S(n, k)$

In this section, we derive our primary formula for $S(n, k)$.

Theorem 2. *For any positive integers k and n , the quantity $S(n, k)$ can be expressed as*

$$S(n, k) = \frac{k(n+1)^k}{2} \sum_{r=0}^{\lfloor k/2 \rfloor} \frac{(-1)^r}{k-r} \binom{k-r}{r} W(n, r), \tag{7}$$

where $W(n, r)$ is the function defined in Section 2.4.

Proof. We consider two cases.

Case I: n is even. In this case, based on Lemma 1, we have

$$S(n, k) = \text{Tr}(M_1^k) + \text{Tr}(M_2^k) + \dots + \text{Tr}(M_s^k),$$

where M_i are the 2×2 matrices defined previously.

If k is even, let $k = 2m$. Utilizing the formula from Equation (5) alongside the values of $\text{Det}(M_i)$ and $\text{Tr}(M_i)$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Tr}(M_i^{2m}) &= (2m) \sum_{r=0}^m \frac{(-1)^r}{r!} \frac{(2m-r-1)!}{(2m-2r)!} [\text{Det}(M_i)]^r [\text{Tr}(M_i)]^{2m-2r} \\ &= (2m) \sum_{r=0}^m \frac{(-1)^r}{r!} \frac{(2m-r-1)!}{(2m-2r)!} [i(2s+1-i)]^r [2s+1]^{2m-2r} \\ &= (2m)(2s+1)^{2m} \sum_{r=0}^m \frac{(-1)^r}{r!} \frac{(2m-r-1)!}{(2m-2r)!} \frac{[i(2s+1-i)]^r}{[2s+1]^{2r}} \\ &= (2m)(2s+1)^{2m} \sum_{r=0}^m \frac{(-1)^r}{2m-r} \binom{2m-r}{r} \left[\left(\frac{i}{2s+1} \right)^r \left(1 - \frac{i}{2s+1} \right)^r \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, we can express $S(n, k)$ as

$$S(n, k) = (2m)(2s+1)^{2m} \sum_{r=0}^m \frac{(-1)^r}{2m-r} \binom{2m-r}{r} \sum_{i=1}^s \left[\left(\frac{i}{2s+1} \right)^r \left(1 - \frac{i}{2s+1} \right)^r \right].$$

Substituting $n = 2s$ and $k = 2m$, we derive

$$S(n, k) = k(n+1)^k \sum_{r=0}^{\lfloor k/2 \rfloor} \frac{(-1)^r}{k-r} \binom{k-r}{r} \sum_{i=1}^{n/2} \left[\left(\frac{i}{n+1} \right)^r \left(1 - \frac{i}{n+1} \right)^r \right].$$

Thus, we conclude that

$$S(n, k) = \frac{k(n+1)^k}{2} \sum_{r=0}^{\lfloor k/2 \rfloor} \frac{(-1)^r}{k-r} \binom{k-r}{r} W(n, r).$$

If k is odd, let $k = 2m+1$. Using the formula from Equation (6) with the relevant values of $\text{Det}(M_i)$ and $\text{Tr}(M_i)$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Tr}(M_i^{2m+1}) &= (2m+1) \sum_{r=0}^m \frac{(-1)^r}{r!} \frac{(2m-r)!}{(2m+1-2r)!} [\text{Det}(M_i)]^r [\text{Tr}(M_i)]^{2m+1-2r} \\ &= (2m+1) \sum_{r=0}^m \frac{(-1)^r}{r!} \frac{(2m-r)!}{(2m+1-2r)!} [i(2s+1-i)]^r [2s+1]^{2m+1-2r} \\ &= (2m+1)(2s+1)^{2m+1} \sum_{r=0}^m \frac{(-1)^r}{r!} \frac{(2m-r)!}{(2m+1-2r)!} \frac{[i(2s+1-i)]^r}{[2s+1]^{2r}} \\ &= (2m+1)(2s+1)^{2m+1} \sum_{r=0}^m \frac{(-1)^r}{2m+1-r} \binom{2m+1-r}{r} \\ &\quad \cdot \left[\left(\frac{i}{2s+1} \right)^r \left(1 - \frac{i}{2s+1} \right)^r \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, we express $S(n, k)$ as

$$S(n, k) = (2m+1)(2s+1)^{2m+1} \sum_{r=0}^m \frac{(-1)^r}{2m+1-r} \binom{2m+1-r}{r} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^s \left[\left(\frac{i}{2s+1} \right)^r \left(1 - \frac{i}{2s+1} \right)^r \right].$$

Substituting $n = 2s$, $k = 2m+1$, we find

$$S(n, k) = k(n+1)^k \sum_{r=0}^{\lfloor k/2 \rfloor} \frac{(-1)^r}{k-r} \binom{k-r}{r} \sum_{i=1}^{n/2} \left[\left(\frac{i}{n+1} \right)^r \left(1 - \frac{i}{n+1} \right)^r \right].$$

Thus, we conclude that

$$S(n, k) = \frac{k(n+1)^k}{2} \sum_{r=0}^{\lfloor k/2 \rfloor} \frac{(-1)^r}{k-r} \binom{k-r}{r} W(n, r).$$

Case II: n is odd. In this case, based on Lemma 2, we have

$$S(n, k) = \text{Tr}(M_1^k) + \text{Tr}(M_2^k) + \dots + \text{Tr}(M_s^k) + n^k.$$

Utilizing similar arguments and analytical strategies as in Case I, we can show that when n is odd, $S(n, k)$ can be expressed as

$$S(n, k) = \frac{kn^k}{2} \sum_{r=0}^{\lfloor k/2 \rfloor} \frac{(-1)^r}{k-r} \binom{k-r}{r} W(n-1, r) + n^k. \tag{8}$$

The detailed proofs of this portion are provided in the Appendix. Next, we demonstrate that Equations (7) and (8) are equivalent. From the definition of $S(n, k)$, we have $S(n, k) = S(n-1, k) + n^k$ for all positive integers n . In particular, if n is odd, then $n-1$ is even, allowing us to apply Equation (7) to arrive at Equation (8). Consequently, Equation (7) is valid for odd values of n . Thus, for any positive integers k and n , we conclude that

$$S(n, k) = \frac{k(n+1)^k}{2} \sum_{r=0}^{\lfloor k/2 \rfloor} \frac{(-1)^r}{k-r} \binom{k-r}{r} W(n, r).$$

Therefore, Theorem 2 is established. □

3.2. Asymptotic Formula for $S(n, k)$ as n Approaches Infinity

In Section 2.4, we defined the function $W(n, r)$. Here, we extend our discussion of this function by examining the asymptotic behavior as n approaches infinity. Recall the expression for $W(n, r)$, given by

$$W(n, r) = \sum_{i=1}^n \left[\left(\frac{i}{n+1} \right)^r \left(1 - \frac{i}{n+1} \right)^r \right].$$

Letting $x_i = \frac{i}{n+1}$, we can express this as

$$W(n, r) = \sum_{i=1}^n f(x_i),$$

where $f(x_i) = x_i^r (1-x_i)^r$. Notably, since $x_0 = \frac{0}{n+1} = 0$ and $1-x_{n+1} = 1 - \frac{n+1}{n+1} = 0$, we find that $f(x_0) = 0$ and $f(x_{n+1}) = 0$. Thus, we can rewrite $W(n, r)$ as

$$W(n, r) = \sum_{i=0}^{n+1} f(x_i) = (n+1) \cdot \sum_{i=0}^{n+1} f(x_i) \frac{1}{n+1},$$

here, $\frac{1}{n+1}$ serves as the width of each subinterval, Δx_i , and as n becomes very large, $\Delta x_i \approx dx$. By the definition of the definite integral, we can thus approximate

$$W(n, r) \approx (n+1) \int_0^1 f(x) dx = (n+1) \int_0^1 x^r (1-x)^r dx.$$

Definition 1. (Beta function). The following function $B(a, b)$ is defined as the Beta function, if it satisfies

$$B(a, b) = \int_0^1 x^{a-1}(1-x)^{b-1} dx,$$

where a, b are real numbers.

Definition 2. (Gamma function). The following function $\Gamma(n)$ is defined as the Gamma function, if it satisfies

$$\Gamma(n) = \int_0^\infty x^{n-1}e^{-x} dx = (n-1)!,$$

where n is a positive integer.

Lemma 3. *The following holds for all positive integers r :*

$$\int_0^1 x^r(1-x)^r dx = \frac{1}{(2r+1)\binom{2r}{r}}.$$

Proof. By Definition 1, we have

$$B(a, b) = \int_0^1 x^{a-1}(1-x)^{b-1} dx.$$

Thus, it follows that

$$\int_0^1 x^r(1-x)^r dx = B(r+1, r+1).$$

By Definition 2, we have

$$\Gamma(n) = (n-1)!.$$

Employing the relationship between the Beta function and the Gamma function [12], we obtain

$$B(a, b) = \frac{\Gamma(a)\Gamma(b)}{\Gamma(a+b)}.$$

This leads to

$$B(r+1, r+1) = \frac{\Gamma(r+1)\Gamma(r+1)}{\Gamma(2r+2)}.$$

Finally, we derive

$$B(r+1, r+1) = \frac{r! \cdot r!}{(2r+1)!} = \frac{r! \cdot r!}{(2r)!} \frac{1}{(2r+1)} = \frac{1}{(2r+1)\binom{2r}{r}}.$$

Thus, Lemma 3 is established. □

Consequently, we have

$$W(n, r) \approx (n + 1) \int_0^1 x^r (1 - x)^r dx = \frac{n + 1}{(2r + 1) \binom{2r}{r}}.$$

Theorem 3. *When the positive integer n approaches infinity, the following approximation for $S(n, k)$ holds,*

$$S(n, k) \approx \frac{k(n + 1)^{k+1}}{2} \sum_{r=0}^{\lfloor k/2 \rfloor} \frac{(-1)^r}{(k - r)(2r + 1)} \frac{\binom{k - r}{r}}{\binom{2r}{r}}, \tag{9}$$

for every positive integer k .

Proof. From Equation (7) in Section 3.1, we express $S(n, k)$ as

$$S(n, k) = \frac{k(n + 1)^k}{2} \sum_{r=0}^{\lfloor k/2 \rfloor} \frac{(-1)^r}{k - r} \binom{k - r}{r} W(n, r).$$

Substituting the result from Lemma 3, we find

$$W(n, r) \approx \frac{n + 1}{(2r + 1) \binom{2r}{r}}.$$

Thus, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} S(n, k) &\approx \frac{k(n + 1)^k}{2} \sum_{r=0}^{\lfloor k/2 \rfloor} \frac{(-1)^r}{k - r} \binom{k - r}{r} \frac{n + 1}{(2r + 1) \binom{2r}{r}} \\ &\approx \frac{k(n + 1)^{k+1}}{2} \sum_{r=0}^{\lfloor k/2 \rfloor} \frac{(-1)^r}{k - r} \binom{k - r}{r} \frac{1}{(2r + 1) \binom{2r}{r}} \\ &\approx \frac{k(n + 1)^{k+1}}{2} \sum_{r=0}^{\lfloor k/2 \rfloor} \frac{(-1)^r}{(k - r)(2r + 1)} \frac{\binom{k - r}{r}}{\binom{2r}{r}}. \end{aligned}$$

Consequently, under the condition that n approaches infinity, the proof is complete. □

3.3. A New Combinatorial Identity

Theorem 4. *The identity*

$$\sum_{r=0}^{\lfloor k/2 \rfloor} \frac{(-1)^r}{(k-r)(2r+1)} \binom{k-r}{r} (2r)^{-1} = \frac{2}{k(k+1)},$$

holds for all positive integers k .

Proof. As n approaches infinity, we observe that $\frac{n}{n+1}$ approaches 1. Consequently, n^{k+1} may be employed in place of $(n+1)^{k+1}$. Thus, we can express an equivalent formulation of (9) as

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} S(n, k) &= \frac{k(n+1)^{k+1}}{2} \sum_{r=0}^{\lfloor k/2 \rfloor} \frac{(-1)^r}{(k-r)(2r+1)} \frac{\binom{k-r}{r}}{\binom{2r}{r}} \\ &= \frac{kn^{k+1}}{2} \sum_{r=0}^{\lfloor k/2 \rfloor} \frac{(-1)^r}{(k-r)(2r+1)} \frac{\binom{k-r}{r}}{\binom{2r}{r}}. \end{aligned}$$

From this, we derive

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{S(n, k)}{n^{k+1}} = \frac{k}{2} \sum_{r=0}^{\lfloor k/2 \rfloor} \frac{(-1)^r}{(k-r)(2r+1)} \frac{\binom{k-r}{r}}{\binom{2r}{r}}.$$

Referring to the Bernoulli-type expression of $S(n, k)$ presented in Equation (2), we have

$$S(n, k) = \frac{n^{k+1}}{k+1} + \frac{n^k}{2} + \sum_{i=2}^k \frac{B_i}{i} \binom{k}{i-1} n^{k-i+1}.$$

This indicates that

$$\frac{S(n, k)}{n^{k+1}} = \frac{1}{k+1} \left(1 + \frac{k+1}{2n} + \sum_{i=2}^k \frac{\frac{B_i}{i} \binom{k}{i-1} (k+1)}{n^i} \right).$$

As n approaches infinity, and for fixed values of k and B_i , we find

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{k+1}{2n} = 0,$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{i=2}^k \frac{\frac{B_i}{i} \binom{k}{i-1} (k+1)}{n^i} &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\frac{B_2}{2} \binom{k}{1} (k+1)}{n^2} \\ &+ \cdots + \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\frac{B_k}{k} \binom{k}{k-1} (k+1)}{n^k} = 0. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, we conclude that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{S(n, k)}{n^{k+1}} = \frac{1}{k+1}.$$

This leads us to establish the following new combinatorial identity

$$\sum_{r=0}^{\lfloor k/2 \rfloor} \frac{(-1)^r}{(k-r)(2r+1)} \binom{k-r}{r} \binom{2r}{r}^{-1} = \frac{2}{k(k+1)},$$

which holds for all positive integers k , thus the proof is complete. □

4. Conclusions

In this paper, we have proposed a new formula for $S(n, k)$ derived from fundamental principles of elementary matrix theory. Unlike previous formulations of $S(n, k)$, which utilize binomial expansions, generating functions, or rely on pre-calculated values of special numbers (such as Bernoulli numbers, Stirling numbers, and hyperharmonic numbers), our approach presents a novel perspective based on matrix traces. Furthermore, we demonstrate that as n becomes exceedingly large, the derived formula can be simplified. Ultimately, we deduce a new combinatorial identity by comparing this simplified expression with the earlier Bernoulli-type formula.

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References

- [1] A. Amir, G. Jeriko, and M. Jusmawati, A method for calculating the sum of diagonal and anti diagonal of power matrices without explicitly calculating its matrices, *J. Phys. Conf. Ser.* **1277** (2019), Article 012038, 9 pp.
- [2] C. Barrera, Sum of powers and harmonic numbers: a new approach, *Res. Math.* **10** (2023), 1-11.

[3] A. Beardon, Sums of powers of integers, *Amer. Math. Monthly* **103** (1996), 201-213.

[4] J. Cereceda, Sums of powers of integers and hyperharmonic number, *Notes Number Theory Discrete Math.* **27** (2021), 101-110.

[5] J. Cereceda, Sums of powers of integers and generalized stirling numbers of the second kind, *Appl. Math. E-Notes* **23** (2023), 449-458.

[6] M. El-Mikkawy and F. Atlan, Notes on the power sum $1^k + 2^k + \dots + n^k$, *Ann. Pure Appl. Math.* **9** (2015), 215-232.

[7] R. Farhadian, A probabilistic proof of a recursion formula for sums of integer powers, *Integers* **23** (2023), #A88, 4 pp.

[8] X. Hu and Y. Zhong, A probabilistic proof of a recursion formula for sums of powers, *Amer. Math. Monthly* **11** (2020), 166-168.

[9] H. K. Krishnapriyan, Eulerian polynomials and Faulhaber's result on sums of powers of integers, *College Math. J.* **26** (1995), 118-123.

[10] D. Laissaoui and M. Rahmani, An explicit formula for sums of powers of integers in terms of Stirling numbers, *J. Integer Seq.* **20** (2017), no. 4, Article 17.4.8, 6 pp.

[11] B. Turner, Sums of powers of integers via the binomial theorem, *Math. Mag.* **53** (1980), 92-96.

[12] W. Wang, Some properties of k -gamma and k -beta functions, *ITM Web Conf.* **7** (2016), Article 07003, 6 pp.

Appendix

Proof of Equation (15) for odd n. When n is odd, we can use Lemma 2 to express $S(n, k)$ as

$$S(n, k) = \text{Tr}(M_1^k) + \text{Tr}(M_2^k) + \dots + \text{Tr}(M_s^k) + n^k,$$

for each matrix M_i where $1 \leq i \leq s$.

If k is even, let $k = 2m$. Utilizing the formula from Equation (5), along with the determinants and traces of M_i , we have

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Tr}(M_i^{2m}) &= (2m) \sum_{r=0}^m \frac{(-1)^r (2m-r-1)!}{r! (2m-2r)!} [\text{Det}(M_i)]^r [\text{Tr}(M_i)]^{2m-2r} \\ &= (2m) \sum_{r=0}^m \frac{(-1)^r (2m-r-1)!}{r! (2m-2r)!} [i(2s+1-i)]^r [2s+1]^{2m-2r} \\ &= (2m)(2s+1)^{2m} \sum_{r=0}^m \frac{(-1)^r (2m-r-1)! [i(2s+1-i)]^r}{r! (2m-2r)! [2s+1]^{2r}} \\ &= (2m)(2s+1)^{2m} \sum_{r=0}^m \frac{(-1)^r}{2m-r} \binom{2m-r}{r} \left[\left(\frac{i}{2s+1} \right)^r \left(1 - \frac{i}{2s+1} \right)^r \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, we can express $S(n, k)$ as

$$S(n, k) = (2m)(2s + 1)^{2m} \sum_{r=0}^m \frac{(-1)^r}{2m - r} \binom{2m - r}{r} \sum_{i=1}^s \left[\left(\frac{i}{2s + 1} \right)^r \left(1 - \frac{i}{2s + 1} \right)^r \right] + n^k.$$

Substituting $n = 2s + 1$ and $k = 2m$, we obtain

$$S(n, k) = kn^k \sum_{r=0}^{\lfloor k/2 \rfloor} \frac{(-1)^r}{k - r} \binom{k - r}{r} \sum_{i=1}^{(n-1)/2} \left[\left(\frac{i}{n + 1} \right)^r \left(1 - \frac{i}{n + 1} \right)^r \right].$$

By using the result from Equation (14), we arrive at

$$S(n, k) = \frac{kn^k}{2} \sum_{r=0}^{\lfloor k/2 \rfloor} \frac{(-1)^r}{k - r} \binom{k - r}{r} W(n - 1, r) + n^k.$$

If k is odd, assume $k = 2m + 1$. Utilizing the formula from Equation (6) and the determinants and traces of M_i , we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Tr} (M_i^{2m+1}) &= (2m + 1) \sum_{r=0}^m \frac{(-1)^r}{r!} \frac{(2m - r)!}{(2m + 1 - 2r)!} [\text{Det}(M_i)]^r [\text{Tr}(M_i)]^{2m+1-2r} \\ &= (2m + 1) \sum_{r=0}^m \frac{(-1)^r}{r!} \frac{(2m - r)!}{(2m + 1 - 2r)!} [i(2s + 1 - i)]^r [2s + 1]^{2m+1-2r} \\ &= (2m + 1)(2s + 1)^{2m+1} \sum_{r=0}^m \frac{(-1)^r}{r!} \frac{(2m - r)!}{(2m + 1 - 2r)!} \frac{[i(2s + 1 - i)]^r}{[2s + 1]^{2r}} \\ &= (2m + 1)(2s + 1)^{2m+1} \sum_{r=0}^m \frac{(-1)^r}{2m + 1 - r} \binom{2m + 1 - r}{r} \cdot \left[\left(\frac{i}{2s + 1} \right)^r \left(1 - \frac{i}{2s + 1} \right)^r \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, we express $S(n, k)$ as

$$S(n, k) = (2m + 1)(2s + 1)^{2m+1} \sum_{r=0}^m \frac{(-1)^r}{2m + 1 - r} \binom{2m + 1 - r}{r} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^s \left[\left(\frac{i}{2s + 1} \right)^r \left(1 - \frac{i}{2s + 1} \right)^r \right] + n^k.$$

Substituting $n = 2s + 1$ and $k = 2m + 1$, we find

$$S(n, k) = kn^k \sum_{r=0}^{\lfloor k/2 \rfloor} \frac{(-1)^r}{k - r} \binom{k - r}{r} \sum_{i=1}^{(n-1)/2} \left[\left(\frac{i}{n + 1} \right)^r \left(1 - \frac{i}{n + 1} \right)^r \right] + n^k.$$

Finally, we conclude that

$$S(n, k) = \frac{kn^k}{2} \sum_{r=0}^{\lfloor k/2 \rfloor} \frac{(-1)^r}{k-r} \binom{k-r}{r} W(n-1, r) + n^k.$$

□